

Extraction chromatographic method of palladium(II) with SRS-100, a high molecular mass carboxylic acid

Bhabatosh Mandal and Uday Sankar Roy*

Department of Chemistry, Visva-Bharati, Santiniketan-731 235, India

Manuscript received 12 March 1998, revised 16 December 1998, accepted 4 February 1999

A selective method has been developed for extraction chromatographic studies of Pd^{II} with SRS-100 (liquid cation exchanger) coated on silica gel as stationary phase. Quantitative extraction of Pd^{II} has been achieved from acetate buffer solution across the pH range 6.0–6.5. The effect of pH, stripping agents, flow rate on extraction and elution have been investigated. Exchange capacity of the exchanger at different temperatures with respect to Pd^{II} have been determined. Pd^{II} has been separated from various elements as well as from several synthetic multicomponent mixtures.

The extraction of Pd^{II} through solvent extraction with sulfur containing extractants (TIBPS)¹, high molecular weight amines², *p*-nitroisoinitrosoacetophenone³ and versatic acid⁴ has been reported but their selectivity is poor. Preconcentration and separation of Pd^{II} have been studied using various supports like silica gel⁵ and alumina⁶. Triocetylamine (TOA)⁷, Amberlite XAD-7⁸ and *n*-capric acid⁹ have also been used as extractants for Pd^{II}, but systematic work on extraction chromatography of Pd^{II} with organic liquid cation exchanger is lacking. The present study reports the systematic work on extraction chromatographic behaviour of Pd^{II} on silica gel impregnated with high molecular mass carboxylic acid, SRS-100.

Results and Discussion

The systematic study on extraction chromatographic behaviour of Pd^{II} with SRS-100 ensured quantitative extraction of Pd^{II} from acetate buffer at pH 6.0–6.5. The complete retention of Pd^{II} was found even at flow rate upto 2.5 ml min⁻¹. The presence of common anion like NO₃⁻, Cl⁻, SO₄²⁻, ClO₄⁻ did not interfere during the extraction. The elution behaviour of Pd^{II} from the column with hydrochloric, sulfuric, nitric, perchloric, acetic, chloroacetic, mixed acid (hydrochloric and nitric), ammonium nitrate, ammonium thiocyanate at different concentrations was tested. Quantitative elution of Pd^{II} from the column, has been achieved only with 0.02 M ammonium thiocyanate. Incomplete elution was observed with hydrochloric acid 1 M, nitric acid upto 8 M, sulfuric acid upto 4 M, perchloric acid upto 6.5 M, chloroacetic acid upto 2 M and EDTA 0.02 M.

Separation of Pd^{II} from binary mixtures : At pH 6.0, Mg^{II}, Ca^{II}, Cr^{III}, Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Zn^{II}, Sr^{II}, Cd^{II}, Pr^{III}, Nd^{III}, Sm^{III}, Gd^{III} and Dy^{III} were not extracted hence passed through the mobile phase. The extracted Pd^{II} was eluted with 0.2 M NH₄SCN and estimated complexometrically¹⁰. Binary mixture containing Pd^{II} with Fe^{III} or Zr^{IV} was passed through the column at pH 2.7, where Pd^{II} passed through with the mobile phase. Extracted Fe^{III} and Zr^{IV} were eluted with 0.5 M H₂SO₄ and 8 M HNO₃ respectively.

Binary mixture containing Pd^{II} with Cu^{II}, Hg^{II}, Th^{IV} and Ce^{IV}, were co-extracted at pH 6.0. The co-extracted metal ions were separated by eluting them first with specific eluents, e.g. Cu^{II} with 0.02 M HNO₃, Hg^{II} with 1 M HNO₃, Th^{IV} with 0.01 M HCl, Ce^{IV} with 0.2 M H₂SO₄ followed by Pd^{II} with 0.2 M NH₄SCN. The results of important binary separations are given in Table 1.

Table 1. Separation of Pd^{II} from binary mixtures

Pd^{II} taken = 3.0 mg, column : (0.8 × 8) cm, flow rate = 1 ml min⁻¹, stripping agent = 0.2 M NH₄SCN, pH = 6.0, 2.7*

Cation	Wt. of metal ion (mg) Added	Relative Recovered	Relative error(%)	Recovery of Pd ^{II} (mg)	Relative error(%)	Eluent used
Cr ^{III}	3.00	2.98	-0.67	3.02	+0.67	-
Mn ^{II}	3.33	3.30	-0.90	3.04	+1.33	-
Fe ^{III}	3.40	3.42	0.59	2.94	-2.00	0.5 M H ₂ SO ₄
Co ^{II}	3.44	3.39	-1.45	3.04	+1.33	-
Ni ^{II}	3.42	3.44	+0.58	2.97	-1.00	-
Cu ^{II}	3.00	3.06	+2.00	2.95	-1.67	0.02 M HNO ₃
Zn ^{II}	2.96	2.98	+0.67	2.95	-1.67	-
Cd ^{II}	3.33	3.30	-0.90	3.05	+1.67	-
La ^{III}	3.40	3.42	+0.59	2.96	-1.33	-
Ce ^{IV}	3.29	3.26	-0.91	3.20	+0.67	0.2 M H ₂ SO ₄
Pr ^{III}	3.20	3.22	+0.63	2.97	-1.00	-
Nd ^{III}	3.26	3.28	+0.61	2.98	-0.67	-
Sm ^{III}	3.24	3.26	+0.61	2.99	-0.33	-
Hg ^{II}	3.00	3.04	+1.33	2.95	-1.67	1 M HNO ₃
Pb ^{II}	3.00	3.02	+0.67	2.94	-2.00	1 M HNO ₃
Zr ^{IV}	3.30	3.34	+1.21	2.96	-1.33	8 M HNO ₃
Th ^{IV}	3.86	3.84	-0.52	3.03	+1.00	0.01 M HCl
U ^{VI}	4.52	4.50	-0.44	2.98	-0.67	-

Separation of Pd^{II} from synthetic mixtures : In order to assess the possible analytical applications the proposed method was applied to separate Pd^{II} from several synthetic mixtures containing Fe^{III}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Pb^{II}, Hg^{II}, Ce^{IV}, Th^{IV}, Zr^{IV} and U^{VI}. In almost all the cases quantitative extractions and separations were achieved. The results of separation of Pd^{II} from synthetic mixtures are given in Table 2. The proposed method is simple, rapid, selective and permits separation of Pd^{II} from Fe^{III}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Pb^{II} and Hg^{II}. Complete work involving separation and estimation of Pd^{II} requires only 2.0–2.5 h.

Table 2. Separation of Pd^{II} from complex mixturesColumn : (0.8 × 8) cm, flow rate=1 ml min⁻¹, pH = 6.0, 2.7*

Sl. no.	Cation	Wt. of metal ion (mg)		Recovery %	Relative error (%)	Eluent used	Eluent vol. ml
		Added	Recovered				
1.	Ni ^{II}	3.42	3.40	99.42	-0.58	-	30
	Cu ^{II}	3.00	3.04	101.33	+1.33	0.02 M HNO ₃	25
	Pd ^{II}	3.00	2.98	99.33	-0.67	0.2 M NH ₄ SCN	30
2.	Zn ^{II}	2.96	2.98	100.67	+0.67	-	30
	Hg ^{II}	3.00	3.07	102.33	+2.33	1 M HNO ₃	25
	Pd ^{II}	3.00	2.92	97.33	-2.66	0.2 M NH ₄ SCN	30
3.	Cu ^{II}	3.00	3.06	102.00	+2.00	0.02 M HNO ₃	25
	Hg ^{II}	3.00	2.98	99.33	-0.67	1 M HNO ₃	25
	Pd ^{II}	3.00	2.96	98.66	-1.33	0.2 M NH ₄ SCN	30
4.	Co ^{II}	3.44	3.41	99.13	-0.87	-	30
	Cu ^{II}	3.00	3.04	101.33	+1.33	0.02 M HNO ₃	25
	Pb ^{II}	3.00	2.97	99.00	-1.00	1 M HNO ₃	25
5.	Pd ^{II}	3.00	2.98	99.33	-0.67	0.2 M NH ₄ SCN	30
	U ^{VI}	3.50	3.47	99.14	-0.86	-	30
	Th ^{IV}	2.98	3.00	100.67	+0.67	0.01 M HCl	30
6.	Pd ^{II}	3.00	2.98	99.33	-0.67	0.2 M NH ₄ SCN	30
	*Fe ^{III}	3.40	3.43	100.88	+0.88	0.2 M H ₂ SO ₄	35
	U ^{VI}	3.50	3.48	99.43	-0.57	-	30
7.	Ce ^{IV}	3.29	3.33	101.22	+1.22	0.2 M H ₂ SO ₄	15
	*Zr ^{IV}	3.30	3.35	101.52	+1.52	8 M HNO ₃	15
	Pd ^{II}	3.00	2.98	99.33	-0.67	0.2 M NH ₄ SCN	30
8.	*Fe ^{III}	3.40	3.43	100.88	+0.88	0.5 M H ₂ SO ₄	35
	Co ^{II}	3.44	3.42	99.42	-0.58	-	30
	Pb ^{II}	3.00	3.03	101.00	+1.00	1 M HNO ₃	25
8.	Pd ^{II}	3.00	2.99	99.67	-0.33	0.2 M NH ₄ SCN	30
	*Fe ^{III}	3.40	3.42	100.59	+0.59	0.5 M H ₂ SO ₄	35
	Ni ^{II}	3.42	3.40	99.42	-0.58	-	30
8.	Pb ^{II}	3.00	3.04	101.33	+1.33	1 M HNO ₃	25
	Pd ^{II}	3.00	2.98	99.33	-0.67	0.2 M NH ₄ SCN	30

Experimental

An Elico LI-120 pH meter, a hot-cum-cold bath and chromatographic column with glass-wool plug at the bottom were used. SRS-100 (Shell Chemical) monocarboxylic acid (C₁₅-C₁₆) was used as a liquid cation exchanger. A stock solution of Pd^{II} (6.0 mg ml⁻¹) was prepared from PdCl₂ (Glaxo) and standardised complexometrically with EDTA¹⁰. Buffer solutions of different pH were made from 0.2 M acetic acid and 0.2 M ammonium acetate.

Preparation of ion-exchange material : The ion exchanger was prepared according to the usual method⁹. The SRS-100 (0.9 ml) coated silica gel (1 g) in distilled water was prepared by centrifugation at 1500 rpm and was taken in a column to achieve a bed height of 8 cm. The column was washed with 4 M HCl. Each exchanger bed could be used at least 25 cycles with its full exchange capacity. The exchange capacity of the exchanger was determined at different temperatures by measuring the milli equivalents of sodium ion absorbed by 1 g of the dry exchanger⁹. The exchange capacity of the exchanger was found to be 1.90–1.96 meq of H⁺/g in the temperature range 25–60°.

General extraction procedure : The desired pH of the exchanger bed (0.8 × 8 cm) containing SRS-100 coated silica gel was adjusted with buffer solution. An aliquot of

the solution containing 3 mg Pd^{II} in 10 ml buffer at pH 6.0 was passed through the column at a flow rate 1 ml min⁻¹. The extracted Pd^{II} was eluted with 0.2 M NH₄SCN solution and estimated complexometrically¹⁰.

References

1. R. D. Walkr and R. Bautista, 'Proceeding of the International Conference on Solvent Extraction Chemistry', 1986, pp.11-107; M. Hidalgo, A Masana, V. Salvado, M. Munoz and M. Valiente, *Talanta*, 1991, **38**, 438.
2. M. Mirza, *Talanta*, 1979, **27**, 107; J. Majumdar and U. S. Roy, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1986, **25**, 1165; Y. Hasegawa, I. Kobayashi and S. Yoshimoto, *Solvent Extract. Ion Exch.*, 1991, **9**, 759.
3. A. D. Sawant and A. M. Khambekar, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1997, **74**, 824.
4. J. Majumdar and U. S. Roy, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1987, **64**, 69.
5. E. M. Bosva, T. A. Bolshova and V. M. Ivanov, *Zh. Anal. Khim.*, 1986, **41**, 991; A. Tong, Y. Akana and S. Tanaka, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1990, **230**, 179.
6. V. M. Ivanov, N. A. Bektova, E. M. Basova and T. A. Bolshova, *Zh. Anal. Khim.*, 1991, **46**, 1512.
7. B. Krystyna and D. Z. Eva, *Talanta*, 1990, **37**, 613.
8. L. Isildar and M. Dogan, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1994, **293**, 319.
9. A. Bandyopadhyay, Ph.D. Thesis, Visva-Bharati University, 1995.
10. R. Pribil, "Chelometry Basic Determinations", Chemapol, Prague, 1961.